

DYNAMIC MODELS IN MENTORING: THE INTEGRATED SKILLS DEVELOPMENT PLANNING (ISDP)

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Abstract

The paper highlights a new mentoring model – The Integrated Skills Development Planning (ISDP), that can be used in higher education in order to provide more flexible, open and coherent framework for the mentoring process. The model has two dimensions: the localization (internal or external) and the specific mentoring phase (identification, analysis and planning). The synthesis of these two dimensions, can help in a better understanding on how to make adequate decisions, in different stages of the mentoring process, both at personal and institutional levels. The paper analyzes the ISDP model in the context of a real mentoring program, that articulates objectives, strategies and methods, evaluation criteria and potential risks.

Keywords: mentoring; mentoring model; creativity, new information and communication technologies, The Integrated Skills Development Planning

According to several experts, mentoring can be defined as a relationship that is established between a more senior individual (mentor) and a lesser skilled or experienced individual (protégé), that is intended to develop and grow the skills, knowledge, confidence, and cultural understanding of the protégé to help him or her succeed, whilst also assisting in the development of the mentor (Johnson & Ridley, 2004). Given the multiplicity of interpersonal situations and the high number of variables involved in the mentoring relationship, we consider that the mentoring process, particularly in the context of higher education, requires models that are robust, flexible and dynamic.

In the process of analyzing different mentoring models, it is important for the participants to start with establishing objectives and evaluation criteria such as: to identify their own professional development options both for past events and for the next period; to respond assertively to workplace requests (both from superiors and colleagues), starting from a clear understanding of one's own personal and professional needs and interests; to better understand the behavior of colleagues at work, avoiding to misinterpret their values, attitudes and ideas; to better identify the personal and professional capacities that can be used at work for promotion; to be more flexible in the personal and professional decisions she takes by analyzing their

consequences; to use a professional development model that allows him to make easier decisions in identifying, analyzing and planning activities, in relation to personal objectives.

In order to reach the mentoring objectives, the participants can select different strategies, methods and techniques, in accordance to the mentoring needs, context and experiences. Such strategies and methods can include: a) Questioning technique; b) Listening technique; c) The technique of silence; d) The technique of reflection; e) Summarizing technique; f) Reframing; g) Motivation technique. Several useful techniques, suggested by Megginson and Clutterbuck are: a) Career Pathing; b) Issues Mapping; c) Capacity Management Model and d) Consequence matrix technique. The same authors offer a clear presentation of mentoring phases, that can be used to choose specific methods and techniques adequate to the requirements of each mentoring stage: 1. Establishing and managing the counseling and mentoring relationship; 2. Establishing specific objectives; 3. Clarification and understanding of situations; 4. Facilitating the process of self-knowledge; 5. Understanding the behavior of other people; 6. Overcoming obstacles; 7. Stimulation of creative thinking; 8. Decision-making techniques; 9. Taking action; 10. Managing the clients' own behaviors; 11. Building wider networks of support, influence and learning; 12. Review and termination of counseling or mentoring relationship.

But because even the best situational analyzes and decisions can sometimes be insufficient, one of the main roles of a mentor is to support the client in the process of taking action. ISDP (Integrated Skills Development Planning) is an excellent dynamic model that could facilitate discussion and reflection on three main levels (see Figure 5): (1) Identifying the position and skills the client aspires to; (2) Gap analysis regarding the gap between current skills and desired / needed skills; (3) Concrete action plan towards achieving the desired skills. The analysis might be better understood in terms of internal context (the customer) and external context (the organization).

	Identification	Analysis	Planning
External	What skills are necessary?	The difference between the requested and necessary skills	How can I be helped by the organization?
Internal	What skills do I have?	The difference between the requested competences and the skills that I have	What is my plan to reduce the gap?

Table 1. Integrated Skills Development Planning Model

In evaluating the degree of success, the achievement of the initially established objectives will be taken into account, expressed operationally by: a) the degree of client satisfaction in relation to the mentoring program, expressed by the position on a Likert scale, with values from 1-5; b) identifying at least three options for each decision taken on a managerial level in a two-week interval; c) correctly identifying at least four potential consequences for at least two managerial decisions and two personal decisions within a two-week interval; d) developing the ability to say no to unreasonable requests in at least half of the situations identified in a two-week interval; e) identifying several professional development scenarios by using career path analysis and exploring their implications on a personal level.

We must also take into consideration that there may be several risks in applying mentoring techniques, including: (a) client resistance, caused by some attitudes or experiences formed over time. In this case it is necessary to explore the causes of the client's resistance and use techniques better adapted to his needs; (b) the techniques proposed in the project may not work. In this situation, other appropriate mentoring methods can be explored; (c) low compatibility between mentor and client; in this case, it is advisable to explore the causes (related to the way of communication, personal style, etc.) and possibly select another mentor, if it is in the client's best interest; (d) the duration of the mentoring program may be insufficient to resolve the client's problems. In this situation, the mentor and the client can take stock of the activities at the end of the mutually agreed period and then discuss the possible extension of the mentoring period, as appropriate.

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